

Conference: Exploration of Computation and Information Technology for Disaster Management (ECITDM14)

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Disasters are unavoidable, unexpected and unwanted tragedies all over the world. The number of disasters both natural and manmade across the globe is increasing dramatically over the period of time and space. Disasters cause damage to billions of human lives, property and infrastructure. Even though, at a comprehensive level, considerable multi / inter disciplinary technical advancement is made, the impact of disaster is still enormous. Disaster management has become a very important subject area that needs serious and immediate attention due to the large number of disasters and massive damage caused by it.

A survey by Government of India states that, India's geo-climatic conditions as well as high degree of socio-economic vulnerability makes it one of the most disaster prone countries in the world, making one among the first ten. As the number of disasters and the loss associated with it is huge effective disaster management play a crucial role and making it the need of this hour. Effective and efficient disaster management schemes will minimize the disaster and impact.

In recent times there has been an increasing awareness in the importance of planning and disaster preparedness. Being prepared for a disaster means also being prepared for its impacts and decisions required during an emergency. This Conference is expected to focus, outline and highlight the common pre- disaster and post disaster issues which need to be addressed to come out with disaster recovery planning. The Conference is also expected to throw some light on peace, prosperity in relation to disaster management outlining the benefits of disaster planning and the value of understanding the requirements before and after a disaster occurs.

This conference will provide a good platform for exchange of ideas on how to best set up a good knowledge-base on disaster management, mitigation and recovery and mechanisms utilizing the latest trends and developments in the field. The most relevant aspect of this Conference is

what are the computational and information technology tools and techniques, roles and responsibilities of the key players in the entire scheme.

The use of social media before, during and after disasters has quickly proven to be one of the fastest and best ways of getting emergency information out to the public. Having an effective emergency social media plan utilizing the computation and IT developments is now a must for any credible company, organization and community. The conference also is a platform to address and review in detail how technology and social media can be used effectively in such an eventuality through participative mechanisms.

In addition, lessons learned, best practices and tips will be shared with attendees on how to harness the technological power before, during and after disasters. As disaster planners, we have a responsibility to adopt and adapt to help us better respond to and prepare for disasters. This conference is hoped to go beyond the awareness and the need to plan the individual components required to develop and implement an effective disaster management plan.

Cooperation in disaster management is a key element of building peace, progress and prosperity. Effective disaster management encompasses efficient coordination among large number of government and nongovernmental organizations. The main challenge is how to educate the people to deal with unforeseen situations rather than panic and be a victim of circumstances by engaging in active joint initiatives on issues ranging from disaster management to disaster-reduction mechanisms and disaster-mitigation schemes. Disaster management is a catalyst for deeper partnership between various groups from all walks of life addressing a common problem by cultivating mutual trust between the public through awareness of Disaster Risk Reduction mechanisms.

It is hoped that at the end of this Conference participants will take home the seriousness, awareness and importance of participative joint efforts needed in situations arising out of calamities caused by natural and manmade disasters.

ECITDM14-Convener

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